

The First Law of Thermodynamics and the Abstraction to a Lack of Information in a Deterministic System Part 3

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In Parts 1 and 2 and also in the first two references listed in Part 1, a deterministic system, namely a particle with $pp/2m$ moving in a one-dimensional box, is analyzed using classical statistical mechanics. In particular, the second reference listed in Part 1 starts with the math equation $d(pI) = I dp + p dI$ and multiplies it by $(p/m) 1/I$ to establish the first law of thermodynamics to a deterministic system.

Here we try to argue that a statistical treatment of such a classical system arises because one focuses on collective work, i.e. $-Pressure dI$. Pressure is due to the particle elastically bouncing off the walls and so the work becomes linked to the collective change dI and not dp (change in momentum). Ultimately, however, this is a Newtonian problem and so $d(pp/2m)$ is due to the change dp , but in statistical mechanics, such a change is seen as dissipation or heat. Thus, classically one would write: $d(pp/2m) = Force dI$, with Force having nothing to do with pressure. In statistical mechanics, pressure seems to be the key idea. $F=dp/dt = dp/dI v(ave)$ (Newtonian treatment) is not equivalent to $P dI = (p/m) (1/I) dI$. To take the statistical viewpoint seriously, one has to focus on the pressure, i.e. an average force on the wall with elastic collisions and treat the actual loss of $pp/2m$ as linked to heat. We argue that ultimately the statistical view of the deterministic system yields $d(pp/2m)$ with dI , the collective work not being of interest in the Newtonian picture. Thus, the statistical picture seems to be linked to the constraint $I=constant$ more than any kind of random or probabilistic feature, we argue.

Statistical Mechanics and the Notion of Constraint

Statistical mechanics seems to be strongly linked to the notion of a constraint. In particular, particles in a gas are restricted/constrained to a fixed volume. Changing this volume is then linked with a very specific constraint based or collective type of work:

$-PdV$ or $-P dI$ in one dimension ((1))

This type of collective work does not consider directly the dissipative nature of collisions as pressure is based on elastic scattering of the particles against the wall. As a result, any dissipative (momentum changing interactions of the particles) must be linked with a heat associated term TdS .

The constraint is linked with an equilibrium scenario and so in the statistical mechanical approach, one thinks in terms of changes to the equilibrium. This seems to be why a pressure term based on elastic scattering with no dp is used with dI . In Newtonian mechanics, there is no such view of equilibrium.

Newtonian Mechanics

In Newtonian mechanics, one simply considers a collision without any constraints. If two particles collide, momentum is conserved, but in general kinetic energy is not and so there is some kind of dissipation in terms of kinetic energy. This dissipation, however, is not called heat, it is called:

$$dE = d(pp/2m) \quad ((2))$$

In other words, there is a change in energy, but it is due to the collision

$$\text{Integral } F \, dx \quad ((3))$$

with force having nothing to do with the notion of pressure, i.e. elastic scattering.

Deterministic Particle Bouncing Back and Forth in a 1-Dimensional Box

A classical particle bouncing back and forth in a 1-D box of length l undergoes elastic scattering at the walls and is constrained in space. If one considers only Newtonian mechanics, then for $pp/2m$ to change, one requires a collision which changes p , i.e. there is no longer an elastic collision at the wall, because this seems like the only place where a collision may occur. If the wall length l remains fixed, this inelastic collision generates energy in the wall which one may call lost heat, i.e.

$$d(pp/2m) = \text{lost heat} \quad ((4))$$

The wall does not move and so there is no collective energy.

It is possible, however, that an inelastic collision occurs at the wall and the wall moves a little, i.e. dl . This suggests that:

$$d(pp/2m) = dE \text{ is linked with a loss in momentum as well as a collective work } dl \quad ((5))$$

In terms of Newtonian mechanics, one may write:

$$dp/dt = \text{Force} \rightarrow dl = v \, dt \text{ so } dp = v/dl \, \text{Force} \quad ((6))$$

((6)) has nothing to do with pressure or even the constraint as one considers a collision at the wall without really caring that the particle has been bouncing back and forth elastically.

We argue that it is only if one focuses on the elastic bouncing of the constrained particle, that the notion of pressure arises. It seems that it is pressure which gives rise to the classical statistical viewpoint because one associates a collective work with:

$$-PdI = -nRT dl = - T dl = - p/m dl \quad \text{if } dE = d pp/2m = .5 T \quad ((7))$$

One may note that ((7)) is not the same as ((6)). The notion of pressure is based on elastic scattering of the particle at the wall and so any dp must be linked with dissipative conditions (heat). Thus, by imposing ((7)), even though dp may occur at the wall, one is forced to introduce a second term:

$$TdS \quad ((8))$$

To retrieve $d(pp/2m)$ and eliminate $-PdI$, the elastic collective work. Thus, we argue that Newtonian mechanics does not really disappear in a classical statistical mechanical analysis.

In particular, if one considers the Sackur-Tetrode equation (1):

$$T dS = T d \ln(l) + T/2 d \ln(pp/2m) \quad \text{where } E = pp/2m \text{ and } T = p/m$$

Thus: $p/m dl/l = P dl$ and cancels the pressure work $- P dl$. The second term of TdS then accounts for dp , i.e. dp is a dissipative result. From the Newtonian point of view, one would only focus on this dissipative term and ignore the pressure situation due to elastic scattering and the constraint. We argue that one may thus consider a deterministic system from two different points of views, but that the statistical one requires one to take the notion of pressure, i.e. elastic scattering and constraint seriously.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the notion of a statistical description of a deterministic particle bouncing elastically in a constrained length l arises because one focuses on the notion of pressure, i.e. a force due to the elastic change in p (no dp) and dl . Pressure is associated with a constraint and an equilibrium viewpoint and so one considers changes from equilibrium, unlike Newtonian mechanics. If dp changes, i.e. $d pp/2m = dE$, then this must be considered as a dissipative situation. As a result, there is a TdS term linked with dissipation and $-PdI$, but TdS contains exactly PdI to cancel $-PdI$ and the Newtonian term $d pp/2m$ which appears as a type of heat type term. In classical mechanics, it would simply be considered an inelastic collision. Thus, the two scenarios are not incompatible, it is just that the statistical one focuses on a collective work due to dl which is linked with no change in dp . If dp actually changes at the wall, this is considered a TdS feature.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sackur%E2%80%93Tetrode_equation